

About seeking economical and ecological balance

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1. Preface

Nowadays, more and more people are aware of problems such as global warming and the rise of sea levels. The world is already aware of the importance of protecting our environment and the ecosystem. But at the same time, it is also important for us to maintain economic development in order to ensure social stability and political stability. So what we need now is to seek a balance between ecological development and economic development to make our society more sustainable. However, it also seems like there are a lot of controversies between the two. It would be hard to find an absolute middle spot between ecological development and economic development. In this article, I would like to address two major questions about seeking a balance between ecological and economic development.

2. How do we ensure economic development?

The first tricky aspect of establishing a balance between economic development and ecological development is obviously—how do we ensure ideal economic development? Even before that, how do we define ideal economic development? The definition of economic development is programs, policies, or activities that seek to improve the economic well-being and quality of life for a community. Many countries such as Venezuela and Zimbabwe still suffer through high inflation where the value of their currency is incredibly unstable. This rise in inflation was usually caused by an imbalance in supply and demand, or a disruption in supply. This will generally lead to a decline in purchasing power and lead to poverty. Thus, we can tell that it is very important for countries to keep their economic development on the right track so that we are in the “green zone of the doughnut.” However, setting goals for economic development is also tricky. The economy will have to decide if they want to focus on short-term development or long-term development, and they also need to arrange the distribution of resources accordingly. Therefore, setting a feasible goal and putting it into action is not simple but it is very essential to ensure the stability of our society and the sustainability of our future (Fig. 1). Doughnut economy is a model to ensure that no one falls short on life’s essentials (from food

Figure 1: The Doughnut Economy [1]

and housing to healthcare and political voice), while ensuring that collectively we do not overshoot our pressure on Earth’s life-supporting systems.

Doughnut economy is a model to ensure that no one falls short on life’s essentials (from food and housing to healthcare and political voice), while ensuring that collectively we do not overshoot our pressure on Earth’s life-supporting systems.

3. How do we ensure ecological development?

Another tricky factor of seeking “the eco-balance” is how to approach an ideal ecological development. It’s not hard to notice that human activities usually result in harm to the environment. For example, development in agriculture usually results in soil erosion and deforestation. It is obviously essential to secure this planet that we survive upon. However, it is very challenging to approach an ideal ecological development since the ecosystem is way older than the species of *Homo sapiens*; humans do not have a perfect

understanding of nature. In addition to that, not everybody in the world's population acknowledges the importance of keeping a sustainable environment, but it is really important for the whole world to make an effort to secure the environment. Some people in impoverished areas and areas of conflict have no extra time and energy to think about the environment since they need to focus on individual survival.

Negative impacts of economic development on environment and ecosystem When people discuss economic development and ecological development, they usually consider them as opposing and controversial. In fact, they are partly opposing each other since sometimes economic development comes with damage to the environment. For example, the industrial revolution in the 19th century led to pollution, deforestation, poor hygiene in urban areas, and exploitation of resources. An inevitable damage to the environment as a consequence of economic and human development is very confusing when seeking a balance between economic and ecological development. Sometimes ecological development and economic development contradict each other since if we focus on ecological development extensively, it will cost a lot of money and there is a possibility that it will lead to the government's budget deficit.

4. How should we manage resources?

Resources are important for any kind of development. However, there are always limited resources that will be available for us to use. So the arrangement and management of resources became a key factor to consider when talking about seeking a balance between economic and ecological development. There is always an opportunity cost when people choose to use resources for different things. For example, if we use building materials to build a factory instead of an animal protection base, our opportunity cost would be the loss of biodiversity. What makes this even more tricky would be the properties of different resources. The production possibility curve is not always a straight line. A specific kind of resource might be more efficient in impacting ecological development than impacting economic development. To demonstrate this, a piece of metal could be used to make a metal chair or to put together a wooden chair. However, you can make more wooden chairs with less metal. Thus, metal would be a more efficient resource when making wooden chairs. The most efficient and feasible way of arranging resources while seeking a balance between economic and ecological development is still waiting for us to discover.

5. Human development-Science and technology

Notice that our society does not stick to the stationary phase. It always works like a solar system in which we look both at the movement of planets inside the system and the

trajectory of the mobile system. While our society "orbits" around our sustainable development goals, we also need to consider overall human development. While ecological development might seem as opposite to technological development due to scarce resources, the process of ecological development also needs the aid of technological innovation. One does not happen without the other, just like two complementary goods. For instance, the development of electric vehicles reduces the amount of pollution from burning fossil fuels. This is an awesome example that shows how the progression in more advanced technology, which normally requires the depletion of resources and harms the environment, actually possesses a net beneficial effect in society. This shows that we also need to put effort into scientific and technological development. However, the tricky part comes in when people are indeterminate of whether or not the newly developed technology will have an overall harm or benefit toward the environment, which makes the situation even more complicated regarding making decisions and resource distribution.

5.1. People's support

Not a single development can be accomplished without the population's support. The process of biological conservation requires the effort of every citizen in the country. However, the action of acknowledgment and awareness among the general public is still progressing slowly. The tricky part of this is that elites will be able to acknowledge the importance of sustainable development, but there is still a large population of people who are more likely to focus on short-term profits that come as a result of economic development instead of long-term benefits brought by ecological development. For example, paper is generally cheaper than plastic as a packaging material. It is also stronger in structure and has a longer life span when compared to paper. However, plastic is harmful.

5.2. Necessities to support the society

We do need to first ensure that our people get enough resources to live a decent life before thinking about "the eco balance". Thus, it was seen as an obstacle in the way of ecological development. Providing people with resources usually comes with the exploitation of natural resources. A simple demonstration of this would be clean water. 70 percent of our planet is covered in water, but only about three percent of Earth's water is fresh water. Of that, only about 1.2 percent can be used as drinking water [2]. But now, access to clean water is already a severe problem in various areas around the world. Therefore, providing necessities for people is also a challenge that we need to face when attaining a more sustainable world.

5.3. Energy sources

Although nowadays a sizable portion of our total energy source is renewable energy, fossil fuel is still a big deal for us. In 2021, renewables and hydroelectricity made up nearly 14 percent of the world's primary energy use, with fossil fuels (oil, natural gas, and coal) accounting for 82 percent (down from 83 percent in 2020), and nuclear energy accounting for the remaining 4 percent [3]. Burning fossil fuels will lead to global warming, but not burning fossil fuels would mean that we won't have enough energy to support our daily activities.

5.4. Use of land

Another very important and scarce resource on our planet would be land. It's probably one of the most crucial resources for both ecological and economic development. However, the distribution of land can also be a challenging task to do. If we use lands for human activities, then the area of forest and the habitats for animals will decrease and therefore damage the ecosystem and harm biodiversity. But if these lands are not in use, it will slow down human development and economic development.

6. Ending remark

In conclusion, the pursuit of a balance between economic and ecological development is a complex approach that requires careful consideration. It involves various aspects that must be taken into account to ensure the preservation of a more sustainable future. By acknowledging the elaborated aspects of economic growth and environmental conservation, we can work towards finding innovative solutions that promote both prosperity and the well-being of our planet.

References

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